

18th April 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Mr. M V Manoj Naag**, a student of **Srinivas College of Hotel Management & Tourism** has done his Industrial Exposure Training with Trident Cochin from **13th December 2021** to **17th April 2022**.

During the training period, his performance was found to be good.

We wish him all the best for his future endeavors.

For **EIH Associated Hotels Limited**
Unit **Trident Cochin**

Anju D Sajeev
Deputy Human Resources Manager

